

NextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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Annex 1: Safeguarding equal opportunities in hiring processes

Annex 2: Term of Reference for NextGEMS Hackathons (ToR)

1 Executive summary

In this report we describe the gender and training strategy in NextGEMS. It consists of our view on gender equality in science and specific activities planned to promote equality and work against unconscious biases. Second, we review our training strategy and describe the various aspects of it, most of them being rooted in our hackathon meetings. As part of the deliverable, the full Terms of Reference (ToR) for a participation in hackathons (by external scientists) is attached in a separate document and mentioned in the report.

2 Conclusion & Results

Project PIs are provided with guidelines for a fair treatment of all genders in hiring processes. Project members are made aware of points of contact for gender issues and discrimination. As part of the training strategy, a document on Terms of Reference (ToR) was written and the necessary measures for a first application process starting in February 2022 for external early-career scientists at hackathons were taken.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of NextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

NOTE: Given that fair and unbiased working conditions, as well as suitable training are essential to meet all project objectives, we consider that this deliverable directly contributes to the overall objectives listed below.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	yes
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	yes

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	yes
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	yes
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	yes
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	yes

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP1	Relevance in this deliverable?
Day to day project management	yes
Scientific coordination including quality assurance (KPI) and risk assessment	no
Data management	no
Ensure efficient innovation management, managing exploitation of project results	yes
Supporting communication and dissemination activities	yes
Clustering with EC, regional and international projects/programmes	yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

This report is split into two parts: first, we describe the gender dimension in NextGEMS, before we elaborate on our training strategy. The latter includes a document Term of Reference (ToR) for the participation at Hackathons.

4.1 Gender

In agreement with the Horizon 2020 Program on Promoting Gender Equality in Research and Innovation¹ we see five ways for promoting gender equality within the NextGEMS project.

1. promoting female role models
2. equal representation of all genders in meetings and presentations
3. fair treatment in hiring processes
4. using gender-neutral language
5. raising awareness of unconscious biases

Female role models

Great care was taken in the assignment of PIs leading one of the four research themes in NextGEMS. The project itself as well as almost all themes are co-lead by a male and a female PI (but for Storms& Ocean) and all PI teams consist of both a early-career and a more experienced scientist. That way, we hope to have approachable PIs in every theme and we foster the representation of women in leadership positions. In total, gender balance of the consortium is considerably stronger than the average in its discipline, from its advisory board (one third female) to its executive board (3 out of 7), to project PIs (38 %)².

Equal representation

In meetings, especially the hackathons, we keep an eye on equal representation of all genders. Whenever there is a choice based on the scientific background, we give preference to traditionally under-represented genders as well as early career scientists for holding presentations or leading a working group. In our first hackathon in October 2021 we had an almost equal share of male (53 %) and female speakers (47 %) in the main talks. Only within the result presentations the share had a skewness towards male speakers which was instead in line with the ratio of participants in the hackathon (female: 34 %, male: 62 %, diverse: 3 %).

Our main communication of the project itself, the people, as well as the upcoming results are presented in VideoBlog (Vlog) entries. The respective dissemination activities lead by WP10 will adopt a gender- and diversity-aware approach when engaging with stakeholders, and when designing communication approaches. By keeping an eye on equal representation of gender we hope to inspire many potential young female scientists.

Fair treatment in hiring processes

We formulated and distributed a one-pager with guidelines for hiring processes among the project PIs (see attached Annex 1). With this, we want to raise awareness of the importance to make the hiring process rather *fair* instead of *equal* base on a study by Gaucher, Friesen and Kay, 2011. *fair* includes a specific wording in the job description, family-friendly working conditions if possible, and a selection committee with equal representation.

Gender-neutral language

Not only in job descriptions, but also in all other documents and meetings we aim to use gender-neutral language and encourage all project members to follow us in this respect. For instance, the MPI-M checks its job advertisements through gender decoder websites to make ensure language neutrality (an example, also available in the section 5 below: <http://gender-decoder.katmatfield.com/>).

Language shapes our perception and gender should not play a role in our scientific work. By using gender-neutral language we not only prevent women from being overseen, but rather address all genders including those that we summarize here under the term diverse. From an anonymous survey made in conjunction with the first hackathon we know that we have non-binary people in our project. We would like them to feel as welcome as everyone else. In this respect, we also want to point the EC to the issue of reporting the project members gender in the European Commission online tool where only binary options are available.

Raising awareness of unconscious biases

We aim to raise awareness of gender issues in science by openly addressing them and discussing statistics, personal experiences and ways forward in our project meetings. We start with a plenary discussion on unconscious biases in science, with a focus on gender, at the upcoming Cycle 2 hackathon in Vienna in June/July 2022.

Where can NextGEMS members find help in case of any gender issues and discrimination?

¹<https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/promoting-gender-equality-research-and-innovation>

²gender is based on people's names if not explicitly stated differently.

There are several levels for support and conflict solutions:

- all NextGEMS Beneficiaries have a local institution that can be approached in case of gender issues and discrimination.
- the NextGEMS Project Office and through it, the gender and equal opportunity resources of the Max Planck Society provide help on various levels by trained professionals³⁴. The Project Office is run by women and can be reached at nextgems_office@mpimet.mpg.de.
- also, our project Co-coordinator Dr. Irina Sandu is responsible for Good Scientific Practice and gender issues, while ultimately, the NextGEMS Executive Board needs to resolve conflicts in case all other measures fail.

4.2 Training

The training strategy of NextGEMS is rooted in our core project meetings in form of hackathons. What is a hackathon? Hackathons are communal exploration, analysis and development activities – all various forms of ‘hacking’. In these meetings people from the project, as well as invited external participants will form groups, analyse simulation outputs, develop new tools, discuss puzzling results and new ideas. The training aspects are manifold and we summarize them in the following under training in data handling, knowledge transfer, and training in science communication.

Training in data handling

The size of simulation output reaches into the Terra and Peta Byte region nowadays confronting scientists with new challenges. Traditional tools and workflows are often suboptimal to work with such large datasets. Therefore, we follow the concept of server-side processing, which keeps the data at the modelling centers and allows users to interact with it using web based scripting environments. In every hackathon, participants get a basic training needed to access and work with the simulation output, including lectures in good scientific practise such as version control, FAIR⁵ data, or collaborative scripting platforms. Such one-day intensive data training workshops at the beginning of hackathons give especially the early career scientists (ECS) tools at hand to conduct their research and follow their scientific interests within the project.

Knowledge transfer

The development of technical skills described in the previous paragraph provides all hackathon participants independent of the stage in their scientific career a chance to start *from scratch* and develop workflows to cope with large datasets. This might actually be a point where the traditional knowledge transfer in science reverses and early career scientists can teach more experienced scientists in effective new tools while sitting next to each other all with their fingers on their laptops. The working atmosphere in our first hackathon in Berlin was open, friendly and with discussions on equal footing, letting innovative ideas decide rather than hierarchy. Nevertheless, the knowledge of experienced scientists, project PIs, and the technical staff from modelling centers is extremely important and finds its way into the hackathons through discussions on the science questions, latest simulation design, active support in analysing and interpreting the data as well as organizing and guiding the so-called Challenge Problems for each hackathon.

The Challenge Problems build a bridge between earth system scientists and related science application fields, such as renewable energies and fisheries. Stakeholders from respective sectors are invited to the hackathons and work together with project scientists on the implementation of workflows that lead to suitable output for the application communities of earth system models.

Another important knowledge transfer node in NextGEMS that is worth mentioning here are our project advisors. The group of advisors consists of world-recognized experts from various fields ranging from earth system science to science communication. They all agreed to bring in their expertise and attend selected hackathons to get in direct contact with all project members including the those at an ECS stage.

Building up and extending networks

Hackathons are huge networking events! Especially ECS have the possibility to get to know their peers as well as the more experienced scientists in small groups while hacking together or over a chat with coffee or at lunch. Knowing the people and also being surrounded by a friendly atmosphere lowers the barrier of asking questions. Asking questions is at the root of having discussions and advancing an understanding of those many facets that earth system science offers to us.

³<https://www.mpg.de/central-gender-equality-officer>

⁴<https://mpimet.mpg.de/en/institute/6140>

⁵Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Training in science communication

At the heart of the project's communication strategy is our *Video Blog (Vlog)*. While the PIs that also lead a research theme already had their first training and videos recorded during the Cycle 1 hackathon in Berlin, further *science explainer* and *Get to know a scientist* videos are planned for the years 2022/2023. In either the Cycle 2 or Cycle 3 hackathon we will include a basic training in science communication that shall strengthen particularly the younger researchers to become active communicators of their work in front of a camera. While Vlogs are an innovative tool to communicate science to a broader community, there is also the possibility of project scientists to present and discuss their research in the weekly Office Hour or in institute colloquia that are established activities at all institutes participating in NextGEMS. Especially ECS are encouraged to travel to project member institutes for a research visit and hold a colloquium on their latest results.

While science communication is a major component of NextGEMS, we plan further soft skill courses in our virtual office hours and at hackathons. Those will be in smaller frames and cover topics such as the above mentioned unconscious bias discussion, networking for hackers, clean coding, good scientific practice, code - life - balance, or publication mania.

Next to the above mentioned training components, NextGEMS especially aims to provide training for early career scientists (ECS) in an open and welcoming environment. In our first NextGEMS Executive Board meeting on 21 October 2021, Divya Praturi was elected to represent the ECS interests in our project. While PhD and PostDoc positions are still in the process of being filled at the moment, we plan a half-day ECS event with a strong socializing component at the next (Cycle 2) hackathon in June/July 2022. In addition, there are developing plans for a longer ECS event in form of an additional hackathon in between the development and application phase of the project in summer 2023.

The youngest among ECS might be Master students and early stage PhDs. NextGEMS aims to not only include the project ECS, but reach out to and invite ECS especially from countries with less of a tradition in climate science. Therefore, we provide funding in form of stipends that enable and cover the participation at hackathons. External participants will have access to all the training and data described above and will mostly work on the mentioned Challenge Problem with guidance provided by members of the lead science themes.

All external participants will have to comply to the project rules that are defined in the Terms of Reference (ToR). The ToR describes the preparation and post-processing to hackathons as well as the invitation of external participants and expectations placed on them. The ToR is a main component of this deliverable and attached to this document.

5 References (Bibliography)

Gaucher, Danielle and Friesen, Justin and Kay, Aaron C.: *Evidence That Gendered Wording in Job Advertisements Exists and Sustains Gender Inequality*. Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, July 2011, Vol 101(1), p109-28. <http://gender-decoder.katmatfield.com/static/documents/Gaucher-Friesen-Kay-JPSP-Gendered-Wording-in-Job-ads.pdf>

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)

This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)
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6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

yes

The delay is due to Covid infections among project members in charge of the report and an unfavourable timing with the seasonal holidays. The delay was approved by our EC PO.

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This deliverable is strongly linked to all other WPs as equal opportunities and proper training build the basis for a successful working experience within NextGEMS.

In particular, WP10 will actively strive for equal opportunities in their dissemination activities.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 hackathon 19.10. – 22.10.2021 in Berlin

11 Full track of publications and IP

No publications so far.

Safeguarding equal opportunities in hiring processes

NextGEMS Project Office, January 2022

Female scientists are underrepresented in STEM and non-binary people often face discrimination. We are convinced that gender should not play a role in science and if we want to recruit top scientists from a sufficiently large pool, we need to actively work against discrimination and promote talented female scientists at an early career stage. The wording in job advertisements is a crucial step towards more equality in science, as shown by a paper by Gaucher, Friesen and Kay, 2011¹.

Guidelines for job advertisements

There are ways to formulate job descriptions such that they attract applicants from all genders. A simple way to check whether your job description is formulated in a gender-appropriate way is provided through the evaluation tool <http://gender-decoder.katmatfield.com/>, which developed out of the above mentioned publication. By applying the tool you can revised specific terms/wordings in order to address members of all genders.

Please consider (if appropriate):

- Including next to technical skills also some soft skills in the job requirements, e.g. “good communication skills, ability to work self-responsible”
- Including opportunities for further (self-)training and development, as well as describing your network inside the institute as well as with the broader scientific community
- Offering part-time and home office possibilities
- Making an open and widespread job announcement in case of a male-dominated workplace surrounding

Guidelines for job interviews

The institute’s Equal Opportunity Officer should always be included and explicitly named in job interviews to ensure a fair treatment of all genders.

Please also consider offering the job applicant the possibility for an informal meeting with one of the ECS from your working group.

Please help to make employees feel welcome in the NextGEMS project, regardless of their gender, nationality, religion, disabilities, age, cultural origin or sexual orientation. Thanks :)

¹ Gaucher, Danielle and Friesen, Justin and Kay, Aaron C.: Evidence That Gendered Wording in Job Advertisements Exists and Sustains Gender Inequality. Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, July 2011, Vol 101(1), p109-28

Term of Reference for NextGEMS Hackathons (ToR)

NextGEMS Project Office, January 2022

This ToR is created for the implementation of the project Hackathons and represents the basis of the activities and obligations for participation.

1. Background Information

The NextGEMS project aims at, among others, changing the Earth-system modelling paradigm: The computational and data demands of storm-resolving earth system models (SR-ESMs) require new, and more inclusive, ways of working. New workflows in form of Hackathons and Scrums will short circuit the value chain and involve a broader community in Earth-system modelling. We use especially the **Knowledge Coproduction Hackathons** to advance model development and conduct pilot projects on risk assessment, near-surface renewable energy production, and coastal marine ecosystems and fisheries.

2. Specific objectives

Hackathons are adopted by NextGEMS as our central approach for sharing and developing expertise required to accomplish complex tasks. Analyzing SR-ESMs is at least as challenging as running them, and will be a major task of the NextGEMS community across the development (1) and application (2) phases of the project.

The Hackathons will be carried out by the three scientific themes: *Storm & Radiation (S&R)*, *Storm & Ocean (S&O)*, and *Storm & Land (S&L)*. Scientific questions addressed by the three themes target all four of the Cloud and Circulation Grand Science Challenge Questions of the World Climate Research Programme¹. In addition to leading traditional dissemination and exploitation activities, the fourth theme *Science & Society (S&S)* will work closely with each of the three physical science themes to develop the broad types of activities within Knowledge Coproduction activities at Hackathons. This addresses the Objective 3 of the project (Grant Agreement part B Annex 1 Section 1.1).

More specifically under each research theme:

S&R: Knowledge Coproduction activities in Hackathons focus on wind energy, aiming for example to understand how circulation changes affect the potential of renewable wind energy production globally. Additionally dissemination will build on the legacy of the H2020 CONSTRAIN project to link new insights into cloud feedbacks and climate sensitivity, aerosol forcing, and the stability of the tropical circulation to integrated assessment modelling.

S&O: Development of innovative approaches to estimate primary productivity. Hackathons will be used to assess how the ability to resolve mesoscale circulations in the atmosphere

¹ Bony, Sandrine et al. (Mar. 2015). "Clouds, circulation and climate sensitivity." *Nature Geoscience* 8.4, pp. 261–268. issn: 1752-0894. doi: [10.1038/ngeo2398](https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2398). url: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2398>.

and ocean affects marine productivity and fisheries, and their changes with warming, also through a particular focus on West Africa. Implications of storm-resolving scales and the potential of SR-ESMs to better represent the marine carbon cycle and the oceanic heat uptake under global warming will be evaluated.

S&L: Hackathons are used to understand how circulation and circulation changes are influenced by land-surface heterogeneity and orography, and how they affect the potential of renewable solar energy production globally, as well as frequency and spatial distribution of hazardous weather.

3. Scope of the work

Hackathons are communal exploration, analysis and development activities – all various forms of ‘hacking’. They prioritize working together over lecturing one another. At NextGEMS meetings, our fingers will do the talking. Hackathons build on experiences gained from the DYAMOND initiative, which enabled the project to involve a large international community in the analysis of the model output. They also have the advantage that, if necessary, they can be readily adapted to a virtual environment. Important elements of Hackathons, as planned for NextGEMS, are as follows:

Structure: Three to four-day events involving roughly 50 participants working in teams to perform common analyses. Usually they involve people sitting together at tables working with laptops to analyze model output, not unlike students working on exercises at a summer school. Server-side processing, which keeps the data at the modelling centers and allows users to interact with it using web based scripting environments (Jupyter Notebooks), makes such activities possible. In addition to team building events, Hackathons may incorporate breakout sessions to present evolving results, or short training exercises, for instance in Science Communication. With a roughly eight-month tempo, Hackathons will also encompass other project meetings, including the General Assembly.

Content: Hackathons will address both Model Development and Knowledge Coproduction. Each science theme will organize two hackathons, one each in the development and application phase of the project. Model-development objectives to be addressed in the Hackathons will revolve around fine-tuning and preparing the SR-ESMs for the production runs. Application communities will work with NextGEMS scientists to co-design Societal Challenge Problems in both all Hackathons.

Participants: All research themes will participate in all development phase Hackathons. In addition, external participation will be supported by organizing Hackathons in countries without a strong ESM modelling tradition (e.g., Romania, Austria, Ireland) and by providing project funding for external participants. These NextGEMS-funded external participants will primarily work on Societal Challenge Problems.

Challenge Problems: Each Hackathon will be organized by one of S&R, S&L, or S&O, together with S&S to also have a Knowledge Coproduction component. As an example, S&R will organize a NextGEMS Hackathon with its Knowledge Coproduction focus on renewable energy. Here, NextGEMS scientists working with experts from the wind-energy industry will outline a problem that can be addressed with NextGEMS output. For example, to directly

produce a global atlas of wind power at the turbine height. External participants will work in teams to solve the problem, with coordination provided by members of the lead science themes. The Challenge Problem will help guide the development of the SR-ESMs, and their associated workflows, in ways that better expose their information content to application communities.

In addition - the Scrums:

Scrums will have the character of small informal Hackathons, and involve members of the modelling groups in addition to the NextGEMS Technologists, and selected PIs from the four thematic areas. These will be two to three-day affairs and may often be held virtually.

4. Requested expertise

The minimum requirements for a participation in Hackathons are:

- Strong interest in climate science and Earth system modeling
- Background: if not a member of the NextGEMS project, external participants shall be involved in (or have completed) a Master's program or PhD in either physics, geophysical science, computer science, engineering (ideally renewable energy), economics, or political science
- Language: Participants must be able to properly communicate in English
- Programming skills: a moderate level of programming experience is required

Depending on the Challenge Problem of a respective Hackathon, the Principal Investigators (PIs) of the research theme in charge of organizing the event will describe in more detail the specific skills and abilities that are required for the participation.

Participants are expected to bring their own laptop and software tools needed for them to engage in the Challenge Problem. While there is support in data handling at Hackathons, participants have to ensure a proper setup of a working environment in their favorite programming language, for example Python.

5. Responsibilities of participants

- The participants should have an ongoing awareness of the project background, the progress and its recent discussions
- The Hackathon participants are expected to devote the required time to the role
- The participants are expected to engage and make a contribution to discussions at the daily group meetings and at the plenum
- The participants are requested to fill out the basic information sheet at the beginning of the Hackathon. No sensitive personal information will be requested
- The participants are expected to fill out the feedback questionnaires of the project for further development of the Hackathons
- The participants are obliged to follow the data processing and data protection regulations (GDPR and POPD²)

² <https://gdpr.eu/>

- External participants are requested to sign a NDA – non disclosure agreement – upon arrival at the Hackathon.

6. Data management at and after the Hackathons

Information on data management in NextGEMS is available in the respective Data Management Plan (DMP – Karsten Peters, DKRZ). A first version will be available in February 2022 while the document is subject to continuous updates to adapt to the project development.

As mentioned above, participants oblige the data processing and protection regulations formulated in the GDPR and POPD.

7. Proceedings

The schedule of the Hackathons will be announced in NextGEMS group emails and on the project website at least 4 months prior to the event.

Due to the technical processes and the expected best outcome from the joint efforts of teamwork, the Hackathons will be held as presenting event only. Unless there is an obvious reason and strong need for the project to organize virtual Hackathons, i.e. pandemic situation.

The organizers of the Hackathons are the responsible research theme, the S&S group, the Project Office and the host of the Hackathon. The agenda and all relevant logistic information will be communicated through the project office. The agendas will be set and agreed with the NextGEMS Executive Board (NEB) and distributed in time to the entire consortium for further input. All members of the project have the opportunity to submit scientific questions and items for discussion during the upcoming Hackathon.

NextGEMS offers up to 15 stipend each Hackathon to young scientists for the participation of the entire event. An application is mandatory.

Financial resources have been made available for different target groups: the NextGEMS members, external guests including advisory board members, visitors from the user community as well as the scholarship holders. For each target group there is different procedure to settle cost accounting. Any question related to financial resources and procedures of organization and the participation of the Hackathons will be clarified by Project Office through individual communication.

The contact email address for general issue is nextgems_office@mpimet.mpg.de

8. Hackathon reports

After each Hackathon, the Project Office circulates follow-up material and access to the hackathon summary within 14 days.

The responsible theme is responsible for the technical report of each Hackathon, this will be submitted to the funding agency as project Deliverables. The time schedule of such Deliverables is set by the Grant Agreement and is typically within about 6 months after the Hackathon.

The individual participants at the Hackathons are not requested to deliver any report.

9. Conflict of interest

If participants find themselves with a conflict of interest, they shall immediately disclose this to the project Coordinator who will report and consult with the NextGEMS Executive Board (NEB).

10. The term

This Terms of Reference is effective from (backdated to) 01.09.2021 and continues until the end of the project on 31.08.2025.

All participants will receive a copy of this ToR prior to the Hackathon. Additionally the document is findable and publicly accessible at the project website.